

NOMINATIVE AND EXPRESSIVE FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE STUDY

Narzullayeva Firuza Olimovna

Lecturer of the department Translation studies and Language education at
Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

Annotation: *This article discusses the fact that language has a nominative and expressive function, which is reflected in language elements, especially in words, and their use in English and Uzbek languages.*

Key words: *nominative, expressive, stylistic color, additional meaning, semasiology, pragmatics.*

INTRODUCTION

Language, which is an important means of communication between people, is a nominative, communicative and complex phenomenon. The fact that language has a nominative and expressive function is reflected in the elements of language, especially in words.

Linguists note that there are two different meanings in the language: denotative (main) and connotative (additional) meaning. The additional meaning of the word is called by different names. Such as stylistic color, additional meaning and expressive meaning. The semantics of the word is not limited to the denotative meaning, but the word also has a connotative meaning. In the scientific works of the next period, it was noted that the denotative meanings of language units were thoroughly studied in general linguistics.

Various textbooks, training manuals, and monographic studies have been created on the denotative meaning of the word. However, despite the fact that the connotative meaning exists in all layers of the language, sufficient scientific conclusions have not yet been made about them. This requires strengthening research in the field of semasiology in linguistics.

Types of connotative meaning, their relation to word semantics in cases where the word is taken as a language and speech element, as well as connotative meanings expressed in phonetic means, i.e. stylistic features related to the pronunciation of speech sounds, supersegment phonetics in the language a number of issues, such as the

additional meaning expressed in the means and the study of the connotative meanings expressed in the morphological units, have not yet been fully resolved in linguistics. There are different views on this in linguistics, some scientists say that the connotative meaning of a word is not part of the semantics of a word, while other linguists believe that the connotative meaning is one of the direct components of the semantic structure of a word.

Some linguists define connotation as a part of word pragmatics. In the scientific literature, there are definitions that connotation is attached to denotation, the connotative meaning expression of a language unit, and additional symbols surrounding it.

Connotation is a semantic entity that is included in the semantics of language units, and it expresses the emotive evaluation and methodologically defined attitude of the speech subject to existence. The same kind of pragmatic evaluation is taken into account in the study of connotation in linguistics. Pragmatics is understood in a relatively narrower sense in modern linguistics. In our opinion, pragmatic information, which has a permanent (stable) state in the language, has caused linguistic interest. Based on this opinion, we understand by pragmatics the evaluation of the following three things consolidated by the speaker in the language unit: the entity that is the subject of information, information content and addressee.

The term "pragmatics" is not directly found in the works of academician V.V. Vinogradov, but he notes the presence of real pragmatic information in various units of the language.

"Pragmatics is a word meaning an event, an object, and at the same time, it also means its connections and relations in a dynamic whole, a historical existence. It reflects the understanding of a part of existence" and the relationship of this part to other elements of this existence. It reflects how these relations were understood by the society and the people of a certain period.

It is difficult to trace the first time that the word connotation was used as a term in linguistics. However, it can be said that in the middle of the 19th century, two different meanings of the term "connotation" were formed in English lexicographical literature related to the theory of synonymous dictionaries and the practice of their creation. First, connotation is considered as "additional" (modal, emotional-expressive) elements of lexical meanings that are directly included in the explanation of the word. Secondly, connotation is not included in the direct lexical meaning of the word legal assessment of things and other objects of existence. By the 19th century, it was found that the word connotation has several other meanings (explanations) in addition to the above-mentioned meanings. For example, connotation is the opposite of denotation

(logical view); connotation is the syntactic valence of the word (psycholinguistic view); connotation - figurative meaning based on figurative elements (elements); It is noted that connotation is a non-obligatory, additional secondary (facultative) element of lexical meaning.

METHODS

Connotation, connotative meaning terms in European and Russian linguistics I.A. Melchuk, L.I. Iordanskaya, A.K. Zhalkovsky, K. Buhler. It can be found in the works of accomplished scientists such as Isachenko, R. Tokari, Y. Bartminsky. The evolution of the word connotation and the definition of its various uses by A.V. It is fully covered in the works of Barovsky. However, it should be noted that Y.J. Watley's most famous book of the 19th century "Selection of synonyms" (1951) defined "Synonyms selection" as an addition (modal, emotional-expressive elements) of lexical meanings directly included in the explanation of the word at the beginning of the word. In Russian linguistics, the interpretation of the term connotation was approached through different opinions, V.V. Vinogradov, P.A. Pletnev's A.K. In his letter to Groth (September 29, 1945), he quotes the following: "I found that there are no words in the language that have absolutely the same meaning, because together with the lexical meaning, with each word the brain the idea of age, people, place, life comes. All this is based on a simple example "boroda" and "brada". The first word embodies the Russian in the reader's mind, in the form of a man, a merchant, a priest. The second word brings us to the period of patriarchs (the position of the highest clergy), to the life of the peoples of the East, because this word is embedded in our minds from church (i.e. religious) books; It is clear from the historical point of view, because this term appears in various fields of science. For this reason, although interest in the connotative aspect of linguistic units has increased in recent years, the concept of connotation is interpreted differently in different disciplines.

RESULTS

In particular, in stylistics, connotation is considered as a stylistic meaning, and it is studied by connecting it with an emotional color. In translation studies, connotation is considered as a pragmatic meaning. Semasiologists who study meaning in a systematic aspect look at connotation as an expressive color, an emotional expression. In psychological studies, connotation is approached as semantic associations. Regardless of how this term is evaluated, its main function is the function of influence, which is directly and continuously connected with the pragmatics of speech. This effect occurs in the process of conveying to the addressee how important the expressed

thought is for the speaker. The attitude of the speaker, who is the subject of speech, to existence is considered important. It is rather difficult to understand the preservation of the above-mentioned meanings in the framework of linguistics, because for almost all meanings of the term connotation, current linguistics has detailed and logically clear concepts, that is, the range of modality, evaluation component, semantic-syntactic valence, etc. In this case, only one meaning (explanation) remains for the term connotation, which is the legal evaluation of the related object, which is the name of the given word.

DISCUSSION

When studying the semantic structure of a word, it is noted that there are two types of connotations: inherent connotation - the connotative meaning inherent in a word taken out of context, and adherent connotation - a connotation formed in a word in a certain contextual meaning. In his monograph "Lexical means of artistic image" E. Qilichev expressed his reasonable opinions about this.

Any connotative expressions contain certain symbols characteristic of the denotative meaning the speaker refers to this sign when expressing his pragmatic purpose. For this reason, the subject of denotation performs the function of evaluation and understanding. Therefore, it is necessary to treat connotation not as a simple connecting ring, but as a means of connecting objectivity and subjectivity based on all the meanings of words (and other language units). In the expressions, the certain sign(s) characteristic of the denotative meaning are necessarily expressed. Linguistic researcher M. Mamadaliyeva proves with reasonable facts in her work "The connotative aspect of nominative units in the Uzbek language". Any connotative meaning retains the denotative meaning.

CONCLUSION

It is known that all language units have a connotative meaning. They have been studied to some extent by linguists. Nevertheless, further research in this field, especially the in-depth study of the connotative meanings of phonetic units, is the demand of the times. The different pronunciation of the speech sounds in the word creates different connotative meanings. Such meanings are an addition to the denotative expression in the word, and it is a different relationship between the speaker and the listener: inner excitement, joy and sadness, approval, surprise, supplication, admiration, sarcasm, desire, reflects influence. The connotative meaning expressed in speech sounds is clearly manifested in their paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationship. The sound structure of the speech is organically connected with the content of the

thought and has an artistic value. In the semantics of the word, it is emphasized that there are 2 types of connotation, i.e. inherent and adherent. Adherent connotation is more strongly expressed in artistic speech than in other speech styles. In speech, the color of additional meaning is actively realized not only in different pronunciations of vowels or consonants, but also with the help of supersegmental means. Phonetic methodology, or It should be noted that sound material, syllable, stress and intonation can express different connotative meanings.

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